

A. C. Polarographic Studies of the Complexes of Cu^{++} and Fe^{++} Ions with 2,4-Dihydroxybenzoic Acid in Aqueous Medium

S. L. Gupta, J. N. Jaitly, and R. N. Soni

Complexes of Cu^{++} and Fe^{3+} ions with 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid in aqueous medium have been studied successfully by a.c. polarography. The results obtained are in good agreement with the values obtained by spectrophotometric method except for the dissociation constant (K_c) for the complex between Fe^{3+} ion and the acid.

Tanabe and Hata¹ studied the colour reaction of 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid with Cu^{++} ion. Gupta *et al.*² investigated the nature and composition of the complex spectrophotometrically and conductometrically and established its formula as CuR (R=reagent). Lerner and Trout³ utilised 2,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid for the colorimetric estimation of iron. Jatkar and Mattoo⁴ reported the formation of 1:1 iron-resorcyate complex from the colorimetric measurements, but their potentiometric data indicated the formation of 1:2 and 1:3 complexes in addition to the 1:1 complex.

As no data are available in the literature on the study of the above complexes by polarography, the present work has been undertaken to study these complexes by a.c. polarography.

EXPERIMENTAL

A pure sample of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B. D. H., A. R.) was used for preparing standard solutions. Ferric chloride solution was prepared from ferrous ammonium sulphate⁵ (B.D.H., A.R.) and the iron content was estimated by the oxide method before preparing standard solutions. Sodium salt of 2, 4-dihydroxybenzoic acid (B.D.H., A.R.) was used as the reagent and was recrystallised before use. Other inorganic chemicals used were of A.R. quality of B.D.H. Mercury used for the dropping electrode was purified as described in another communication⁷.

The technique of the measurement was the same as that described by Doss *et al.*⁶, the only modification adopted is described in another communication by Gupta and Sharma⁷. Negative d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the saturated calomel

1. *Ann. Rept.*, 1956, 6, 7.

2. *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, under publication.

3. *Virginia J. Sci.*, 1949, 2, 13.

4. *This Journal*, 1963, 39, 775.

5. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co., Ltd., 2nd ed., 1962, p. 470.

6. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 35A, 27; 1953, 36A, 493.

7. *This issue*, p. 381.

A. C. POLAROGRAPHIC STUDIES OF THE COMPLEXES OF Cu^{2+} & Fe^{3+}

electrode. pH of the solutions was adjusted by Beckman pH-meter (model H2). The experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of $30^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$. The constants of d.m.s. were: $m = 3.559$ mg./sec., $t = 2.3$ sec./drop in 0.1M-KCl, open circuit. A 0.1M solution of sodium acetate was used as the supporting electrolyte.

DISCUSSION

Gupta and Chatterjee⁸ have shown that a.c. polarography can be used with advantage for the quantitative study of the complex metal ion. The peak potential $(E_p)_c$, corresponding to the reduction of (ic) to (ous) state of the complex metal ion in both the complexes studied, shifts to more cathodic potentials with increasing concentration of the complexing agent, whereas the peak potential $(E_p)_s$, corresponding to the reduction of the (ous) state of the complex metal ion to the metal amalgam, remains constant, irrespective of the concentration of the complexing agent. This shows that Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions only form the complex with the reagent.

According to Kolthoff and Lingane⁹, the formula and dissociation constant of the complex ion of a metal, soluble in mercury, may be expressed by the relations:

$$\frac{\Delta(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c}{\Delta \log c_x} = -p \frac{0.0591}{n} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

and

$$(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c - (E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s = \frac{0.0591}{n} \log K_c - p \frac{0.0591}{n} \log c_x \quad (ii)$$

respectively where $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ refer to the reversible half-wave potentials of the complex metal ion and simple metal ion, respectively; ' c_x ' is the concentration of the complexing agent, ' p ' is the co-ordination number of the complex metal ion, ' n ' is the number of electrons involved in the reduction of (ic) to (ous) state of the complex metal ion, and K_c refers to the dissociation constant of the complex.

The above equations can also be applied for deriving the formula of the complex as well as its dissociation constant by a.c. polarography if $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_c$ and $(E_{\frac{1}{2}})_s$ are replaced by $(E_p)_c$ and $(E_p)_s$, i.e. their peak potentials, respectively.

Curve 1 in Fig. 1 shows a straight line on plotting $(E_p)_c$ corresponding to the reduction of cupric ion vs. log concentration of acid(B) with a slope of -0.57 volts. From this slope, the value of ' p ' comes to be 0.97 with $n=1$ from eq. (i), showing thereby that the formula of the complex is CuR which agrees with the formula obtained by spectrophotometric and conductometric methods⁸. From the equation for the straight line through the experimental points (curve 1, Fig. 1), it is found that $(E_p)_c$ is -0.187 volt vs. S. C. E. at acid concentration of 1.0M. From this value and the value of $(E_p)_s$ calculated from thermodynamic data¹⁰, i.e. -0.079 volt vs. S.C.E., the value of K_c was calculated from

8. *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1964, under publication.

9. "Polarography", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, Vol. 1, 1952, p. 214.

10. Meites, "Polarographic Technique", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1955, p. 129.

equation (ii) as 1.489×10^{-3} which agrees fairly well with the value of 0.65×10^{-3} for K_0 found spectrophotometrically.

FIG. 1
Curve 1: pH = 5.5.
Curve 2: pH = 3.0.

Similarly curve 2 in Fig. 1 represents the straight line plot of $(E_p)_c$ corresponding to the reduction of ferric ion vs. log concentration of acid having a slope of -0.047 . From this slope the value of the number of acid molecules combined with one Fe^{3+} ion comes out to be 0.80 with $n = 1$. The corresponding formula may be represented as FeR which agrees with the formula obtained spectrophotometrically¹¹. Further, the value of K_0 for FeR , utilising $(E_p)_c = -0.482$ volt vs. S.C.E. (from curve 2 at acid concentration of $1.0M$) and $(E_p)_c = +0.525$ volt vs. S.C.E. (standard reduction potential of Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} system), is found to be 8.91×10^{-16} . This is very much different from the value of K_0 (0.91×10^{-4}) obtained spectrophotometrically¹¹. It is difficult, however, to explain this discrepancy at present and needs further investigation.

The authors are thankful to the authorities of B.I.T.S., Pilani, for providing facilities and to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of a fellowship to one of them (R.N.S.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BIRLA INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY & SCIENCE,
PILANI, RAJASTHAN.

Received September 18, 1964.